

Design and manufacturing of the all-composite visual display support structure of the SIMONA research simulator.

Peter de Haan

Centre of Lightweight Structures TUD - TNO

Joint venture between the Faculty of Aerospace Engineering of the Delft University of Technology and the TNO

Institute of Industrial Technology, Delft, The Netherlands

e-mail: P.A.J.deHaan@lr.tudelft.nl

Abstract

The support structure of the visual display system for the research simulator of the International Centre for Simulation, Motion and Navigation (SIMONA) has been designed and built. This paper discusses the design procedure within which two competitive design concepts have been developed. Furthermore, the manufacturing and assembly of the construction is highlighted and some tests to components and the assembled structure are described. Finite element analyses have been used to make a trade off study to both design concepts. The research simulator is to be used for scientific research in the field of human motion perception, improved simulation techniques, new flight procedures and man-machine interaction. To be able to perform the research desired, the main requirements for the simulator were low weight and moment of inertia in combination with high rigidity. In this way not only a good response to input controls could be achieved but also a high first natural frequency for use up to 15 Hz. This high first natural frequency enables the reproduction of high frequency vibrations that often accompany the initial response of the actual vehicle.

Both design concepts are based on the use of carbon fiber reinforced composites (CFRP) in view of their high specific strength and stiffness properties. In the first design concept, a truss of carbon fiber reinforced tubes mounts the visual display system to the flight deck. In the second design concept, only a small part of the structure is a space truss, the rest of the structure is an assembly of sandwich structures with CFRP facings. As a result of the trade study, the design concept with the sandwich parts was found most appropriate for further engineering. The most important issues of the detailed engineering of this concept are discussed.

The composite parts of the structure, flat, single and double curved sandwich structures with PVC foam core and CFR epoxy facings, were manufactured using the vacuum infusion technique. The last step in the realization of the simulator was assembly of the separate parts with close tolerance bolts to prevent loss of overall stiffness and failure. During the project, several tests have been carried out. The first test concerned the stiffness of the space truss segments. To prevent overestimation of the rigidity of the space truss in the FEM model, a complete segment of the truss including joints was built and tested for its rigidity. From the test, an equivalent stiffness is defined for the bar elements in the FEM model. After the assembly was completed, a start has been made with motion tests to check if the performance of the simulator meets the requirements.

Introduction

The International Centre for Research in Simulation, Motion and Navigation Technologies SIMONA is a co-operation between the faculties of Mechanical, Electronical and Aerospace Engineering of the Delft University of Technology. SIMONA is developing a new simulator for research in the improvement of simulation techniques and its mathematical models, the processes involved in human motion perception and the man-machine interaction. The Centre of Lightweight Structures, a cooperation between the faculty of Aerospace Engineering of the Delft University of Technology and the Netherlands Organisation for Applied Science TNO, has been responsible for the design, analysis, manufacturing and assembly of the motion platform of this SIMONA research simulator (SRS). The motion platform mainly consists of fiber reinforced composite parts. In this paper, first the SRS will be discussed in general. Based on the list of requirement to the simulator, a short overview of the design, analysis and manufacturing of the SRS motion system and flight deck will be given. The list of requirement, the motion system and the flight deck are the bases of the design of the visual display support structure. The design, analysis, manufacturing and assembly of this structure will be discussed in the rest of the paper.

The SIMONA research simulator

Essential for high quality flight simulation is the reproduction of physical (vestibular, visual and aural) and environmental (surroundings, instrument panel) cues closely resembling the cues encountered in real flight. These cues are the result of the control activities undertaken by the pilot and external influences. According to [1], the pilot receives information about the state and change in state of the vehicle mainly in two ways. First, visual information is received through the central vision. Second, motion cues are derived from the visual and vestibular system. Of these two, the visual information requires longer processing time in the human brain than the vestibular cues. The vestibular cues are therefore very important to create realistic motion simulations.

For close resemblance between the simulator and the vehicle being simulated, it is very important that the onset of motion of both systems correspond. High-frequency vibrations followed by more smooth accelerations often accompany the initial response of the actual vehicle. To increase the level of fidelity of the simulation, high frequency ground contact dynamics, flight through turbulence with the presence of structural flexibilities and vibrations should be incorporated in the range of flight conditions.

In practice, this is not easily achievable: commercially available motion platforms are heavy and difficult to set in motion accurately due to the packaging of on-board equipment. To be able to research the topics mentioned, it was decided to start the development of a completely new simulator which should take full advantage of an integrated design of all major systems: the hydraulic actuators, the visual display system and the flight deck.

Before the concept design of the SRS was started, the general layout of the simulator was determined. This general layout was the starting point for the synthesis of a list of requirements that in its turn will be used as a basis for the concept design of the flight deck of the SRS.

figure 1 The 6 hydraulic actuators with dummy motion platform

figure 2 The flight deck and the visual display subsystem

General lay-out

The SRS consists of two main systems, the hydraulic actuator system (figure 1) and the motion platform. The hydraulic actuators have been designed to the special requirements of the SRS but will not be discussed here except for their interface to the motion platform. The motion platform consists of several subsystems, see figure 2: the visual display system, the interiors for all vehicles to be simulated, the control system and the flight deck. This paper will focus on the design of the flight deck and the support structure of the visual display system.

Before the concept design of the SRS was started, two major decisions, greatly influencing the layout of the simulator, were taken. In the first place, it was decided that the hydraulic actuator system should enable motion with six degrees of freedom. 6 hydraulic actuators in the set-up plotted in figure 1 are used. The second decision concerns the visual display system. Of two alternative, commercially available visual display systems, a panorama display system and a monitor based display system, it was chosen to equip the SRS with the panorama display system as plotted in figure 2 and figure 3.

The panorama display system consists of three projectors that project a computer-generated representation of the environment of the vehicle to a back projection screen (bps). This bps is provided with a semi-translucent film through which the image will be visible at the side of the back projection screen furthest from the projectors. The pilot at the flight deck of the simulator is watching a 180° spherical mirror that is directed towards the bps. In this way, the pilot will experience a most reliable and accurate illusion of a three-dimensional environment in which his vehicle is moving.

figure 3 The visual display system

List of requirements

To be able to accomplish the research the SRS is developed for, it is important that cues that accompany the onset of motion of the aircraft being simulated can be reproduced by the SRS. This means that high-frequency ground contact dynamics, flight through turbulence with the presence of structural flexibilities and vibrations should be incorporated in the range of flight conditions that can be simulated. Since these cues are most rapidly noticed by the human vestibular system, a research simulator should be able to apply translational and angular accelerations to the human vestibular system that match the accelerations of either the vehicle being simulated or the effect being researched.

In [1], it is stated that aircraft encounter excitations in the frequency range up to 15 Hz. The SRS should be able to reproduce these vibrations. Next to reproduction of these vibrations itself, also the quality of the vibrations, indicated by the delay and the phase of the vibrations in relation to the flight control input signals of the pilot and the response of the real vehicle is very important. The highest fidelity of the simulation is achieved when the SRS meets the next major requirements.

Modern training simulators consist of a flat steel base frame and the tendency is to mount more and more equipment to this base frame. To compensate for the loss of dynamic performance due to the increase of weight, training simulators are provided with more powerful hydraulic actuators. The increase in power of the actuators increases the weight of the actuators, but a more rigid, thus heavier, base frame is necessary. In this way, a negative spiral towards heavier and less controllable simulators is entered. It can be shown that the extra power will not restore the capacity of the simulator to reproduce accurate vibrational modes in the range of frequencies desired. Therefore, the first main requirement the SRS should meet is that the mass of the SRS kept low as possible.

The second main requirement concerns the mass moment of inertia properties of the motion platform. The center of the three theoretical interface points of the motion platform to the hydraulic actuators can be seen as the center of motion of the simulator. This point has the shortest possible distance to the hydraulic actuators of the motion system and is the location where all mass of the simulator should be concentrated to minimize the power to set the simulator in motion and to maximize the response to the flight control systems. All simulator parts distant from this point will increase the inertia and the flexibility of the simulator and thus the simulator performance. To limit this decrease, the mass moment of inertia of the assembled simulator with respect to the center of the upper gimbal circle should be minimized.

The third main requirement is derived from the demand that vibrations up to 15 Hz are included in the motion envelope of the SRS. To avoid structural damage to the simulator due excessive deformation or acceleration when the SRS get into resonance, the first natural frequency of the motion system should be higher than 15 Hz. The first two main requirements, low mass and low mass inertia properties, will support in achieving this, but in addition the third main requirement is that the rigidity of the motion platform should be as high as possible.

In the fourth place, the motion platform should be able to withstand all loads imposed on it during operation of the simulator including emergency situations.

Next to the four main requirements, low mass and inertia and high rigidity and strength, some extra requirement must be met:

- The interior should consist of modules that can be removed and replaced easily to enable the simulation of motion of other automotive vehicles e.g. cars, trucks, ships, trains and helicopters
- No part of the motion platform or the flight deck should interfere with the hydraulic actuators to avoid limitation of the motion envelope of the SRS.
- The flight deck and the support structure of the visual display system must allow for an undisturbed experience of the image generated by the visual display system and should not obstruct the light beams of the projector nor the area between the mirror and the back projection screen.

- The flight deck must be light tight so that no scattered light can decrease the quality of the visually displayed environment.
- The visual display system will be purchased and mounted to the flight deck. The mounting inserts in the visual display system are fixed and cannot be redefined. The flight deck should provide support for the visual display system at these interface locations.
- Also the locations of the interface between the motion system and the flight deck have been chosen and the flight deck must be capable of carrying the loads introduced by the hydraulic actuators.

figure 4 Shuttle right sandwich shell and reinforcing beams

The flight deck: an integrated composite shell structure

The design of the flight deck is based on optimum use of the design space available and the integration of as much functions in one single structure as possible. Three volumes determine the design space available. The motion envelope of the hydraulic actuators forms the first volume. The motion platform should not interfere with the motion system in any possible position of the simulator. The second volume is the space that is required for undisturbed perception of the view generated and displayed by the visual display system. The third volume is the enclosing volume of all the modules representing the interiors of the vehicles to be simulated.

In figure 2, curves are plotted that tightly enclose all the interior modules but do not interfere with the visual display system and the motion system. The double curved surface described by the curves will be made of a fiber reinforced sandwich structure to meet the requirement of low mass. If necessary, this sandwich will be reinforced and stiffened using composite beams to meet the strength and stiffness requirements. Reinforcement will be required at locations where high loads are introduced to the shell and near large cutouts. The composite shell will have two major cutouts: one for the window and one for the entrance. The window cutout in the shell should enclose the windows of all vehicles to be simulated. The resulting shell, called the shuttle, is plotted in figure 4.

figure 5 First and second eigenmode shape of the shuttle at 27.1 Hz (left) and 39.0 Hz (right)

The finite element analysis and the detail design of the shuttle is described in [4]. In figure 5, the first two eigenmode shapes are plotted. These two mode shapes in the shuttle are important because they induce the first two eigenmodes of the shuttle in combination with the visual display support system.

figure 6 CFRP lower girders on the sandwich inner skin

figure 7 Foam and wooden inserts of the beams

figure 8 CFRP webs and upper girders of the beams

The double curved shuttle in figure 4 can not easily be manufactured using metals. The moulds required are too expensive for single piece production. Therefore, it was decided to use composite materials in combination with the wet lay-up procedure in a negative mould as the manufacturing process.

The outer facing of the sandwich shell is manufactured in two halves, each in a negative mould. Then the negative moulds are put together, the halves of the outer facing are joined by a laminated scarf joint, the core is applied and covered with the inner skin. On top of this inner skin, the lower CFRP girders of the beams are laminated (figure 6), the cores of the beams are placed (figure 7) and covered with CFRP webs and upper girders (figure 8). The complete shuttle is depicted in figure 9. In figure 10, the shuttle is mounted to the motion system.

figure 9 The complete shuttle

figure 10 Shuttle mounted to the motion system

The visual display support structure

The visual display support structure has been designed with the flight deck and the motion system depicted in figure 10 as basis using the requirements as listed above. Starting point for the design was the design space available. The mirror, the back projection screen and the projectors must be mounted at fixed locations in relation to the design eye point. These items, in combination with the volume through which the light of the projectors traces and the structural items already present, are the bounds of the design space depicted in figure 11. The design requirements for the visual display support structure are the same as discussed above for the flight deck.

Conceptual design

Several design concepts have been developed and evaluated in [3]. Only two were considered as possible solutions for further evaluation: the upper crown concept depicted in figure 12 and the canopy - petal concept depicted in figure 13. Both concepts have several items in common which will be discussed first. From the design of the shuttle it was found out that the eigenfrequency requirement was difficult to meet. A preliminary finite element (fe) analysis pointed out that this would also be the case for the complete simulator including the visual display system and its support structure. Therefore, it was decided to base the design of the visual display support structure on the results of a preliminary eigenfrequency analysis. This analysis revealed two important eigenmodes that are indicated in figure 14. The common parts of the two design concepts form load paths to prevent deformation in these modes. The lower edge of the mirror is mounted to the shuttle with a truss of CFRP tubes that are directly connected to the beams, frames and stiffeners in the

shuttle. This open truss structure, called the lower crown, will be made light tight using cloth. The end wall is placed in the vertical plane through the aft edges of the mirror and has the function of an external frame. It reduces the deformation of the shuttle in the second eigenmode. The ear panels support the aft edges of the mirror to the shuttle in forward direction and try to prohibit deformation in the first eigenmode. On top of the ear panels, the projector platform (ppf) is mounted. Bookshelf support are used to support the free upper part of the end wall to the ear panels. Not visible in figure 12 and figure 13 is the shield. The shield is depicted in figure 19 and is mounted to the end wall and the lower edge of the back projection screen to prevent it from vibrating.

figure 11 Design space available for the visual display support structure

figure 12 Upper crown concept of the visual display support structure

figure 13 Canopy - petal concept of the visual display support structure

figure 14 The first two eigenmodes of the simulator

The difference between both design concepts is the structure connecting the upper edge of the mirror to the back projection screen. In the upper crown concept, see figure 12, this connection is established by a truss. This truss consists of CFRP tubes. Light tightness will be provided by cloth stretched between the tubes of the truss. The back projection screen (bps) is attached to the crown. The crown itself is mounted to the end wall and bookshelf supports are used to support the crown to the ear panels.

In the second design concept, the upper crown is replaced by light tight sandwich panels. A canopy is used to support the back projection screen to the end wall. The aft canopy mounts this canopy to the ear panels. The gap between the back projection screen and the upper edge of the mirror is bridged by three petals.

The canopy - petal design concept has the highest first natural frequency and the best producibility and ease of assembly at the lowest cost. This concept was chosen for further analysis, detailed engineering and manufacturing. Except for the CFRP truss, all parts of the visual display support structure are made of sandwich panels that consist of a PVC foam and CFRP facings. Some of these parts are mounted at unfavorable positions far from the center of gravity of the structure. To keep their mass as low as possible, the resin infusion technique is used to manufacture the sandwich parts. With resin infusion, it is possible to achieve fiber volume contents of 50%. Special techniques enable the injection of a complete sandwich in a single injection.

Structural design and analysis

The sizing of the parts of the visual display support structure in the canopy - petal concept has been done with finite element calculations. For that purpose, a fe model was developed in which all composite sandwich parts are represented with shell elements with a layered composition. This enables the correct simulation of the sandwich behavior by taking the core material in to account and also allows for the modeling of all CFRP plies in the laminated facings. The mechanical properties of the sandwich elements are calculated from the properties of the plies.

The visual display support structure has been optimized for the highest natural frequency. It appeared that increasing the axial and the bending stiffness of the separate panels, by increasing the thickness and the lay-up of the facings or the thickness of the core was only effective to a certain extent. An increase in stiffness can only be achieved by adding extra material. At some level, the extra mass of the material added will eliminate the effect of the extra stiffness on the eigenfrequency of the simulator.

The structure has been designed on strength using 6 static ultimate load cases reported in [2]. These load cases have been derived from the emergency situation that all the hydraulic control and safety systems fail and that maximum oil pressure is applied to one of the six hydraulic actuators.

figure 15 CFRP tube test set-up

For the CFRP tubes in the truss of the lower crown, bar elements have been used in the fe model. These bar elements have two nodes with three translational degrees of freedom and they only have an extensional stiffness and a cross sectional area as properties. In reality, the tubes in the truss are provided with aluminum fittings to connect them to the shuttle and the mirror. These fittings have not been included in the fe model. The lower crown is an important load path in the two eigenmodes of the lowest natural frequencies. Therefore, it is important to use the correct extensional stiffness for the bar elements in the fe model. The stiffness of an actual tube including the fittings has been obtained from tensile tests with a set-up depicted in figure 15. A tube with short length was taken so that the contribution of the fittings to the test is relatively large. In this way the stiffness of longer tubes will be underestimated. From the test results, strains measured directly on the tube with strain gauges versus forces from the load cell of the test device, a stiffness of 85 GPa has been calculated. The tubes have an outer diameter of 40 mm and a wall thickness of 3.2 mm. The carbon fibers have 0° and 90° orientation with respect to the tube axis. Because the loads in the tubes are only axial, the amount of 0° fibers is larger than the amount of 90° fibers. The fittings are adhesively bonded to the tubes. The adhesive joint as been designed

using finite difference calculations discussed in [5] to determine the peel and the shear peak stresses in the adhesive. The maximum bar forces from the 6 static load case have been used to check the tubes on buckling.

The most important results of the fe calculations are the first two eigenfrequencies of the complete simulator. These eigenfrequencies have been found at 16.7 Hz and at 17.8 Hz. The corresponding eigenmodes are plotted in figure 16 and figure 17. In the figures, the deformation of the frame to which the end wall is attached and of the shuttle is plotted. The deformation of the shuttle in these two eigenmodes is equal to the eigenmode shapes of the stand alone shuttle plotted in figure 5.

Detail design

After the structural analysis indicated that the canopy - petal concept in theory meets the eigenfrequency requirement of 15 Hz, the detail design was started. In this phase of the design, the details of the structure were elaborated. Many of these details have to do with load introductions and its corresponding stress concentrations.

figure 16 First eigenmode at 16.7 Hz

figure 17 Second eigenmode at 17.8 Hz

The sandwich panels have been provided with inserts at locations of high loads, wooden blocks at moderately loaded locations, steel bushes at highly loaded areas. If required, the laminates determined from the eigenfrequency calculations have been strengthened to carry high local loads.

To assure correct load introduction of the visual display support structure to the beams in the shuttle, tension fittings have been used. In figure 20.b, two tension fittings are depicted that connect the end wall to the shuttle. Not visible in the figure are the corresponding tension fittings inside the shuttle. Each set of two tension fittings assures that the forces of the panels of the visual display structure to the shuttle are introduced to the frames and beams and not to the sandwich skin of the shuttle.

Manufacturing

All sandwich parts of the visual display support structure have been made with the vacuum injection technique. The flat parts (end wall, ear panels, bookshelf support, projector platform) are made on a flat table. The end wall and the projector platform are too big for the table and have been divided in more than one part. All single curved (shield, canopy, aft canopy) and double curved parts (petals) have been made on negative or positive wooden moulds.

a. First facing, inserts and foam

b. Start of resin injection

c. End of resin injection

figure 18 Manufacturing of the end wall

a. Mould and first facing

b. Punctured foam core and flange

c. Resin injection halfway

figure 19 Manufacturing of the shield

The complete products, both facings and the core including all inserts, were manufactured with a single shot injection. After putting the required dry fabric, core and inserts in or on the mould, see figure 18.a and figure 19.a, the complete

package is covered with an air tight foil, see figure 18.b. This foil is sealed at the edges and forms an airtight chamber. By means of a vacuum pump, liquid epoxy is sucked into the dry package of fibers under the foil. Impregnation of facings in contact with the mould and covered by foam is established by providing the foam core with small holes through which the resin will be transported, see figure 19.b. After the injection is finished, the laminate is cured in an oven.

Assembly

Assembly of all separate parts to a complete simulator was a secure job for which a detailed assembly procedure was made. The first goal of this procedure was to mount all three parts of the visual display system in the correct position in relation to each other and in relation to the design eye point. The second goal was to assemble the structure without losing stiffness due to slip in the bolted joints. Therefore, all parts have been bolted together using close tolerance bolts and "lock tight". To be able to place close tolerance bolts it was necessary to drill corresponding holes in separate parts together and then roam them. This requires that two separate parts are hold in position towards each other after which the holes can be drilled. In this way, small tolerance and thus high costs on the dimensions of the parts could be avoided. The problem of holding the parts in position was solved using scaffolds. Some stages of the assembly procedure are depicted in figure 20. The complete simulator in operation is shown in figure 21.

After assembly, the weight of the simulator has been measured using the load cells in the actuators of the motion system. This weight, including the interior representing a wide body aircraft, was 3880 kg and should be compared to 12000 to 18000 kg for commercial training simulators.

a. End wall to the shuttle

b. Tension fittings

c. Ear panel to end wall and shuttle

d. Aft canopy - ppf sub-assembly

e. Canopy and bps to the end wall

f. Mirror to the end wall

g. Petals to the mirror and end wall

h. Truss between mirror and shuttle

i. Overview

figure 20 Assembly of the simulator

Testing

After finishing the simulator, a test program was started. This test program comprehends mechanical tests and motion control tests. Discussion of the motion control tests and the response of the simulator is beyond the scope of this paper. The mechanical tests will be carried out in the near future. It will be determined what the actual eigenfrequencies and eigenmode shapes of the simulator are and if they correspond to the eigenfrequencies and mode shapes discussed above. The information of the mechanical tests, eigenfrequencies and eigenmode shapes will be incorporated in the motion control software to avoid excitation of the eigenmodes.

Conclusions

By means of modern design and analysis techniques, a light and stiff motion platform of a research simulator has been developed. The assembled simulator weighs 3880 kg including an interior representing a commercial wide-body aircraft. Theoretically, the structure meets the most important design requirement of a first eigenfrequency higher than 15 Hz. The calculated eigenfrequencies are 16.7 Hz and 17.8 Hz. The actual eigenfrequencies of the simulator will be measured by mechanical tests.

figure 21 The SIMONA research simulator in operation.

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